

BACTERIOCIN FROM FERMENTED MILK SAMPLE AND WOUND HEALING ACTIVITY

*Sheena E.V.,**Rathna Kumari A.K. and Ramya J

*Assistant Professor, PG Department of Plant Biology and Plant Biotechnology Shrimathi Devkunvar Nanalal, Vaishnav College for women, Chromepet.

**Associate Professor, PG Department of Plant Biology and Plant Biotechnology, Shrimathi Devkunvar Nanalal, Vaishnav College for women, Chromepet

PG Student, PG Department of Plant Biology and Plant Biotechnology Shrimathi Devkunvar Nanalal, Vaishnav College for women, Chromepet.

ABSTRACT

Lactic acid bacteria was isolated and cultured from commercially available milk, curd and rice water using MRS broth and MRS agar and the bacteriocin was isolated from bacteria. Later characterized on the basis of their morphological, physiological, biochemical and molecular properties. Later screened for antiwound healing activity on 3T3 mouse fibroblast normal cell line.

Key words: lactic acid, fermentation, antibacterial, physical, biochemical characterization

INTRODUCTION

Lactic acid bacteria (LAB) are a group of gram-positive, non-spore forming, non-respiring, cocci or rods, which produce lactic acid as the major end product of the fermentation of carbohydrate (Axelson, 1998). LAB are used as natural or selected starters in food fermentation in which they perform acidification due to production of lactic acid flavour. Bacteria from the genera *Lactobacillus*, *Lactococcus*, *Leuconostoc*, *Pediococcus* and *Streptococcus* are the main species of LAB involved. Although several more have been identified but they play a minor role in lactic fermentations [1] LAB are often inhibitory to other microorganisms and this is the basis of their ability to affect the keeping quality and safety of many food products.

Bacteriocins are protein or protein complexes produced by bacteria and have antimicrobial activity against closely related species and various Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria including food spoilage bacteria and pathogens [2] The bacteriocins from lactic acid bacteria (LAB), generally recognized as safe (GRAS) and have arisen a great deal of attention as a novel approach to control pathogens in food-stuffs. In 1925, Bacteriocins were discovered by Gratia when he was involved in the process of searching for ways to kill bacteria which also resulted in the development of antibiotics and the discovery of bacteriophage, all within a span of few years. His first discovery was named colicin because it 129 was produced by killing *E. coli* [3]

In this article the bacteriocin producing bacterium was isolated from traditional product i.e. fermented milk. The isolate was characterized by morphological, biochemical and molecular properties.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Sample Collection

Fermented milk sample was collected from Panangattupakkam, Tamilnadu. It was used for isolation of bacteriocin-producing bacteria. Plate I

Test Microorganisms

The test microorganisms like *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis* were isolated and the pathogenic strains were obtained from Culture Collection Centre, University of Madras, Taramani Campus and confirmed on the basis of Morphological and Biochemical characterization.

Growth media and Conditions

The de Man Rogosa Sharpe (MRS) broth medium, nutrient broth medium and Muller–Hinton agar (Hi-Media Chemicals, India) were procured for production of bacteriocin, bacteriocin assay and antibiotic susceptibility respectively.

Lactobacillus MRS agar medium

Protease peptone - 10.0 g
Beef extract - 10.0 g
Yeast extract - 5.0 g
Dextrose - 20.0 g
Polysorbate 80 - 1.0 g
Ammonium citrate - 2.0 g
Sodium acetate - 5.0 g
Magnesium sulphate - 10.0 g
Manganese sulphate - 0.05 g
Dipotassium phosphate - 2.0 g
Agar - 20.0 g
Distilled water - 1000 ml
pH (at 25°C) - 6.5 to 6

Isolation and screening of bacteriocin producing bacteria from milk samples

All five raw milk samples were kept at 4°C during transport to the laboratory. Serial dilutions of the milk samples were immediately made in sterile distilled water and were spread onto MRS agar (de Mann Rogosa Sharpe) pH adjusted to 5.4 with acetic acid to facilitate the isolation of the genus *Lactobacillus*, and M17 agar (Difco) supplemented with 0.5% lactose (LM17) to isolate other LAB [4]. Plate II The resultant colonies with different morphology were selected. Colonies showing catalase negative reaction were selected for screening of bacteriocin producing isolates [5].

Screening of LAB for Antimicrobial Activity

Preparation of sample filtrate

The LAB isolates were inoculated from petriplates to test tubes containing 6 ml fresh of MRS broth and incubated at 37°C for 48 hrs. The culture broth of each isolate was centrifuged separately for 20 minutes. The supernatant was collected after centrifugation and the cell free neutral supernatant broths was collected for the antibacterial study against selected food borne pathogens.

Media for growth of pathogens

The pure cultures of food borne pathogens namely *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis* were inoculated in nutrient broth. After 24 hours of incubation at 37°C, the culture broth was used for inoculation of the pathogenic strain on nutrient agar plates for the antibacterial activity determination of the sample filtrate.

Composition of Nutrient broth

Peptone - 1.0 g
Yeast extract - 0.5 g
NaCl - 1.0 g
Distilled water - 100 mL
Final pH - 7.0 ± 0.2

Wound Healing activity

3T3 mouse fibroblast normal cell line was obtained from the National Centre for Cell Sciences (NCCS), Pune, India. Cells were maintained in the logarithmic phase of growth in Dulbecco's modified eagle medium (DMEM) supplemented with 10% (v/v) heat inactivated fetal bovine serum (FBS), 100 U/mL penicillin, 100 µg/mL streptomycin. They were maintained at 37°C with 5% CO₂ in 95% air humidified incubator [6].

Characterization of LAB isolates

Morphological characterization

Gram staining

A thin smear of the culture was made, air dried and heat fixed. The slide was flooded with the primary stain (crystal violet) for one minute. It was washed off with water and flooded with the mordant (Gram's iodine) for a minute. After washing off the mordant a decolouriser (alcohol) was added and washed off. The slide then was flooded with a counterstain (safranin) for a minute. The slide was then washed, air dried and observed under the oil immersion objective.

Biochemical characterization [7 and 8]

1. Catalase reaction test

A loop full of overnight grown culture was taken on the surface of glass slide and 1 drop of hydrogen peroxide was added. Observe the slide for 1-2 min. The production of oxygen bubble indicates the positive test and absence of oxygen bubbles indicates negative test.

2. Methyl red test

All enteric microorganisms ferment glucose and produce organic acids. The methyl red indicator which is used in this test, in the pH range of 4 will turn red, which is the indicative of a positive test. At a pH of 6, still indicating the presence of acid but with a lower hydrogen ion concentration, the indicator turns yellow and is a negative test.

3. Voges proskauer test

Voges proskauer test determines the capability of some microorganisms to produce non-acidic or neutral end products, such as acetyl methyl carbinol, from the organic acids that result from glucose metabolism. The reagent used in this test, Barritt reagent consists of mixture of alcoholic alpha-naphthol and potassium hydroxide solutions. Detection of acetyl methyl carbinol requires this end product to be oxidized to a diacetyl compound. This reaction will occur in the presence of alpha-naphthol catalyst and a guanidine group that is present in the peptone of MR-VP medium. As a result, a pink complex is formed, imparting a rose colour to the medium.

4. Citrate utilization test

In the absence of fermentable glucose or lactose, some microorganisms are capable of using citrate as a carbon source for energy. This ability depends on the presence of citrate permease that facilitates transport of citrate in the medium becomes alkaline, the carbon dioxide that is generated combines with sodium and water to form sodium carbonate, an alkaline product. The presence of carbonate changes the Bromothymol blue indicator incorporated into the medium from green to Prussian blue. After incubation citrate positive

culture are identified by the presence of growth on the surface of slants, which is accompanied by blue coloration. Citrate negative will show no growth and the medium will remain green.

5. Indole Test

Tryptophan is an essential amino acid that can undergo oxidation by the way of enzymatic activities of bacteria and converted into metabolic products (indole, pyruvic acid and ammonia) is mediated by the enzyme tryptophanase. The presence of indole is detected by adding Kovac's reagent which produces cherry red colour. The colour is produced by the reagent which is composed of p-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde yielding the cherry red colour. Absence of red coloration demonstrates that the substrate tryptophan was not hydrolysed and indicates an indole negative.

Extraction of Bacteriocins

Chloroform – Methanol (2:1 v/v) was used for crude Bacteriocin extraction. However produced precipitate at Solvent-Aqueous interphase was collected aseptically, solvent was evaporated and precipitate was kept in buffer which was used for antimicrobial study[9]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Isolation of lactic acid bacteria (LAB) from milk samples

Lactic acid bacteria (LAB) were isolated from different unpasteurized milk samples

Wound healing activity were recorded. Plate V In-vitro scratch wound healing assay 3T3 cells were seeded in 6-well plates (8×10^5 cells/well) and grown until reached a confluence of 90-95%, in the optimum culture conditions. In the middle of cell monolayer, a scratch was made by a P10 pipette tip, to mimic a wound, and cell debris were removed by washing with fresh medium. The wound was exposed for 50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of bacteriocins sample for 48 hrs at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere of 5% CO₂. The cell grown in extract-free medium were used as control. Scratch wound closure was analyzed under the inverted microscope (Magnus INVI, Noida) equipped with a digital SLR camera, by acquiring digital images at different time 0th (T₀), 24hr (T₁), 48hr (static imaging).

1] Axelson, L.T. (1993). *Lactic acid bacteria: Classification and Physiology*. In: salminen, INC., New York, USA: 1-63.

2] Choks, Nikita and Desai Hemangi (2012), Isolation Identification and Characterization of *lactic acid bacteria* from Dairy Sludge Sample, Journal of Environmental Research and Development, Vol.7 No.1A. 8.

3] De Vuyst, L.; Leroy, F. Bacteriocins from *lactic acid bacteria*: Production, purification and food applications. J. Mol. Microbiol. Biotechnol. 2007, 13, 194–199.

4] Felice F, Zambito Y, Belardinelli E, Fabiano A, Santoni T, Di Stefano R. Effect of different chitosan derivatives on *in vitro scratch* wound assay: a comparative study. Int J Biol Macromol. 2015, 76:236-41.

5] Guillet A., Proteomic analysis of *Lactococcus lactis*, a Lactic Acid Bacterium. Journal of Proteomics 2003, 3, 337-354.

6] Harrigan W.F. and McCance M.E, Laboratory methods in food and dairy microbiology, Acad. Press, 1st Ed., London, 25-29.(1976)

7] Mahrous H, Mohamed A, El-Mongy M, El-Batal A, Hamza H: Study Bacteriocin production and Optimization Using New Isolates of *Lactobacillus spp.* Isolated from Some Dairy Products under Different Culture Conditions. Food and Nutrition Sciences 2013; 4: 342-356.

8] Stevens, K. A.; Sheldon, B. W.; Klapes, N. A. and Klaenhammer, T. R. (1991), Nisin treatment for inactivation of *Salmonella* species and other Gram-negative bacteria. Appl. Environ. Microbiol., 57, 3613-3615.

9] Van Geel-Schuttená, G.H.; Flesch, F.; ten Brink, B.; Smith, M.R.; Dijkhuizen, L. Screening and characterization of *Lactobacillus strains* producing large amounts of exopolysaccharides. Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol. 1998, 50, 697–703.

10] Zacharof, M.P.; Lovitt, R.W. Bacteriocins produced by *lactic acid bacteria*: A review article. APCBEE Procedia 2012, 2, 50–56.

PLATES

PLATE I: MILK SAMPLE

PLATE II:FN SPREAD PLATED AT [A] 10², [B] 10³ SERIAL DILUTION

PLATE III:PURE CULTURE ISOLATE

PLATE IV: BIOCHEMICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF FM- [A] INDOLE TEST, [B] METHYL RED TEST, [C] VOGES PROSKAUER TEST, [D] CATALASE TEST, [E] CITRATE UTILIZATION TEST

PLATE V: WOUND HEALING ACTIVITY

Normal

Wounded cells

Treated (48 hours-88.23%)

TABLE I: BIOCHEMICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF LB

S.NO	Biochemical tests	LB
1.	Indole test	ABSENT
2.	Methyl red test	PRESENT
3.	Voges Proskauer test	ABSENT
4.	Catalase test	ABSENT
5.	Citrate utilization test	PRESENT

PHYSICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF LB

ISOLATES	FM
Colour	White colour
Shape	Rod shape
Gram's reaction	Gram negative